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Authenticity in Basic Language and Literacy Instruction for Adult L2 Learners in Sweden

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Abstract

This participatory action research study explores how teachers in basic-level *Swedish for Immigrants* (SFI) (study path 1) work with authentic texts to support literacy development among adult migrants with limited prior schooling (LESLLA learners). Data collected over one year comprise classroom observations, collegial reflections, teacher interviews; a questionnaire was completed at the end of the project. Drawing on theories of literacy as socially and culturally situated practices, and on authenticity understood as meaningful language use in real-life contexts, the thematic analysis shows that texts from learners' everyday lives functioned as boundary objects bridging classroom instruction and societal participation. Teaching practices increasingly involved multimodal scaffolding, student-initiated materials, and pedagogical role-plays based on communicative needs, such as dental appointment messages and official notices, used as mediating practices. This fostered a learner-centered, co-constructive pedagogy, enhancing agency and autonomy, transferable beyond school contexts. While challenges related to linguistic complexity of institutional texts and uneven digital access remained, the participatory research process strengthened teachers' professional learning. Overall, the findings underscore that authenticity can enhance emergent literacy development while simultaneously promoting social inclusion and teacher development.

Keywords: LESLLA learners, Swedish for Immigrants, authenticity, action research, professional learning, literacy instruction

Introduction

Adult migrants with little or no school background (LESLLA students) simultaneously develop basic literacy and second language, which creates a double learning challenge (Bigelow & Vinogradov, 2011; Minuz et al., 2022). The *Swedish for Immigrants* (SFI) program provides basic language education for newly arrived adults and is structured into three study paths, with Path 1 designed for adults with little or no prior schooling who develop literacy later in life. Despite its ambitions, SFI has long been criticized for limited equity and insufficient responsiveness to the diverse needs, circumstances, and goals of its learners (Hyltenstam & Milani, 2012; Lindberg & Sandwall, 2007; Swedish Schools Inspectorate, 2018, 2024; Swedish Government Official Reports [SOU 2020:66]). This is particularly problematic for LESLLA learners, whose literacy practices and development are closely tied to everyday experiences and social contexts (Bigelow & Vinogradov, 2011; Condelli et al., 2008; Franker, 2011). Research on literacy as a social practice emphasizes the importance of grounding instruction in learners' lived realities through materials and tasks reflecting daily life and communicative needs (Barton & Hamilton, 2000; Street, 1984). Authentic texts, such as appointment letters, text messages, or public signs, can serve as powerful tools to promote engagement, comprehension, and learner autonomy (Gilmore, 2007; Reinders & Benson, 2017). Previous studies also show that authentic materials can enhance motivation, cultural participation, and pragmatic competence, while posing challenges that require pedagogical adaptation (Willis, 1996). Against this backdrop, investigating the extent to which SFI teachers rely on authentic texts to scaffold learning for LESLLA learners becomes particularly important. The study presents findings from an action research project conducted at an SFI school in Sweden, following teachers' implementations of authentic texts in basic second language and literacy instruction over one year and their perceptions of its impact on teaching and learner engagement. The research questions guiding the study were:

1. What characterizes the teaching practices involving authentic texts?
2. What benefits and challenges do teachers identify for learners in the use of authentic texts?
3. How do teachers perceive students' responses to working with authentic texts?

This study provides insights into how authenticity, understood as situated engagement with everyday texts, contributes to emergent literacy development in SFI and how pedagogical practices such as scaffolding and role-plays function as mediating supports in LESLLA instruction.

Background and Educational Context

Swedish for Immigrants

Sweden has a long tradition of receiving migrants, and in recent years many of them have arrived from regions where access to formal education is uneven (Colliander et al., 2018). Consequently, a substantial proportion of SFI learners begin their studies with little or no prior literacy education (Wedin, 2024a, 2024b). These adults are offered basic language instruction through SFI, where completion is often a prerequisite for further education and labor market participation (Wedin & Norlund Shaswar, 2019). Proficiency in the host country language is widely regarded as crucial for social inclusion and labor market establishment. SFI aims to provide both qualified language teaching that supports communication and participation in everyday life,

society, and work (Swedish National Agency for Education, 2024) that facilitates integration into education and working life. However, investigations¹ and research (Wedin, 2024b) consistently show that teachers often lack adequate competence in basic literacy instruction, and standardized teaching materials are frequently used instead of authentic, multimodal resources adapted to LESLLA learners. This has been identified as a barrier to progression and meaning-making for these students², particularly when instruction insufficiently draws on students' everyday practices and local literacy environments (Wedin & Norlund Shaswar, 2019, 2023). These persistent misalignments between SFI teaching practices and learners' everyday literacy needs formed the pedagogical tension that motivated the participatory action research approach in this study.

LESLLA Learners' Conditions and Literacy Teaching

LESLLA learners are often described as having limited literacy skills, which affect cognitive processes relevant to reading and vocabulary development, including phonological processing and working memory (Da Silva et al., 2012; Kurvers & van de Craats, 2007). Although many learners have strong semantic and pragmatic skills in familiar contexts, they often lack strategies for abstract and symbolic text processing (Ardila et al., 2010; Franker, 2011). Research further indicates that meaning-making in institutional and multimodal texts is often grounded in LESLLA learners' lived experiences, with interpretations based on associations and visual cues rather than institutional text conventions, sometimes resulting in non-target understandings (Altherr Flores, 2019). Learning for this group is therefore typically embedded in concrete interaction and everyday experience (Bigelow & Tarone, 2004; Piccinin & Dal Maso, 2021). As literacy develops, phonological and metalinguistic awareness expand, supporting reading and grammatical development (Kurvers & van de Craats, 2007). These characteristics have implications for how second language and literacy instruction are designed and underscore the need to conceptualize literacy as a continuum shaped by real-world practices and contextual demands (Perry et al., 2018). LESLLA students generally progress more slowly in L2 learning than their schooled peers (Bigelow & Watson, 2013; Klein & Perdue, 1992), underscoring the need for instruction that supports both language and basic cognitive abilities. While these learners often possess strong communicative resources rooted in lived experiences, they require explicit support for developing phonological awareness, abstract representations, and school-related strategies (Bigelow & Schwarz, 2010; van de Craats et al., 2015). Research emphasizes that context-based, functional and authentic approaches that connect to learners' lifeworlds enhance motivation, participation and literacy development (Colliander et al., 2018; Condelli et al., 2008). Effective instruction integrates multimodal media, mother-tongue support and explicit strategy training (Wedin & Berg, 2024), and varied authentic content predicts success in both reading and language learning (Kurvers et al. 2015). In the SFI context, Franker (2011) critiques scholastic, decontextualized literacy teaching for reinforcing deficit perspectives, and instead promotes socioculturally grounded and multimodal practices. Likewise, Wedin (2024b) identifies a need for strengthened teacher competence and materials that combine authentic relevance with systematic literacy development. Consistent research emphasizes that literacy instruction should be directly

¹ Swedish Schools Inspectorate (2018, 2024); Swedish Government Official Reports [SOU 2020:66].

² Swedish society places high demands on literacy (Franker, 2011) and ranks among the top five OECD countries in terms of adults' competences in reading, arithmetic and problem-solving according to earlier PIAAC cycles. The most recent PIAAC assessment (2023/2024) confirms these high societal demands while also showing that a considerable share of adults still lack adequate literacy skills, particularly among foreign-born adults and those with limited educational backgrounds (Statistics Sweden, 2024).

linked to learners' everyday lives and needs (Barton & Hamilton, 2000), by using authentic materials such as work-related documents, signage, forms, and health information, while integrating oral and written language and repeated exposure (Condelli et al., 2008). Because commercial materials often rely on unfamiliar symbolic conventions, teacher-generated and culturally relevant materials are frequently more appropriate for LESLLA learners (Bigelow & Schwarz, 2010).

Theoretical Framework

Authenticity has long been a central concept in second language teaching, especially within communicative and task-based language teaching (TBLT) (Gilmore, 2007; Widdowson, 1978, 1998). The concept has gained further relevance with digital technologies that provide extensive access to real-world texts online. In this discourse, authenticity refers both to textual authenticity (i.e., materials created for real communicative purposes) and to authentic use, where language is employed in socially meaningful ways (Buendgens-Kosten, 2014; Widdowson, 1978). Crucially, authenticity is not an inherent property of the material itself but emerges through learners' opportunities to construct meaning and situate language within socially situated practices. Instruction therefore needs to create learner-oriented contexts that render language socially real within the classroom environment (Skiada, 2021; Widdowson, 1998).

In this study, authenticity is conceptualized as situated engagement with texts from learners' everyday lives, where meaning-making and use extend beyond isolated linguistic forms towards social action. Authentic materials thus provide exposure to language in use, characterized by linguistic complexity, diversity, and functional purposes (Gilmore, 2007; Tomlinson, 2012). Their pedagogical value lies in affective and cognitive engagement, potentially promoting deeper processing, motivation, and communicative competence, when supported appropriately (Gilmore, 2007; Reinders & Benson, 2017). By connecting classroom content to students' lived realities, teaching strengthens students' agency, as they gain practical benefits from what they learn.

The study draws on New Literacy Studies, which conceptualize literacy as socially and culturally situated practices, rather than a set of technical skills (Barton & Hamilton, 2000; Street, 1984). From this perspective, everyday and vernacular literacies constitute important learning resources particularly for adult learners with limited prior schooling, whose literacy practices are often undervalued (Ivanič, 2009). A sociocultural lens is therefore essential, since cognitive-dominant perspectives, as discussed in some research (Perry et al., 2018), risk overlooking identity, context and social participation, even though cognitive research also provides valuable insights into literacy development when not reduced to learners' limitations.

Research further highlights the importance of bridging in- and out-of-school practices and linking instruction to the contexts learners participate in or strive to participate in, outside the classroom. This orientation has been described as *bringing the outside in* through everyday materials and activities and *bringing the inside out* by encouraging real-world use of classroom skills (Baynham, 2006; Sandwall, 2013). Such an approach aligns with communities of practice and situated learning theories, where learning develops through meaningful participation (Lave & Wenger, 1991). This socially situated language learning involves *student agency*, where learners bring issues and texts from their everyday lives into classroom discourse, and *teacher contingency*, meaning teachers' responsive and improvised uptake of these contributions (Baynham, 2006). Such dialogic pedagogy positions learners as co-constructors of instructional content, thus challenging monologic, teacher-controlled interaction. Building on learners' prior experiences

supports meaningful and cognitively accessible learning (Ausubel, 1968; Sexton, 2025) while acknowledging students' voices and experiences supports empowerment and learner agency (Freire, 1970/1993). Continuous participation and action across different contexts – so-called *boundary-crossing* – expand opportunities for understanding and acting within different practices (Akkerman & Bakker, 2011; Engeström et al., 1995). Artefacts that function across contexts serve as *boundary objects*, enabling authentic materials to mediate communication between different worlds (school and everyday life), creating dialogical spaces where the students' experiences and institutional norms meet. Through these encounters, students come to view their everyday lives from a school perspective and vice versa, leading to a renegotiation of their identities as language users (Akkerman & Bakker, 2011).

Previous Research

Prior research highlights three pedagogically valuable features of authentic text: culture, currency, and challenge (Mishan, 2005; Skiada, 2021). *Culture* emphasizes the inseparable link between language and culture where authentic texts serve as “cultural keys” that support schema development and cultural awareness, i.e. cognitive structures that facilitate understanding (Mishan, 2005). This is particularly relevant for LESLLA learners who often lack access to natural linguistic and cultural environments (Jehoul et al., 2025). *Currency* refers to real-world language use and contemporary social contexts, which increases relevance, engagement, and motivation (Berardo, 2006; Skiada, 2021). Compared to traditional textbooks, authentic materials can offer adult-oriented and up-to-date content (Gilmore, 2007). Finally, *challenge* relates to the natural complexity of authentic texts, which can foster confidence, risk-taking, and learner autonomy when supported appropriately (Skiada, 2021). Research stresses that tasks should be adapted, by for instance adjusting the type of activity or level of support rather than simplifying text, to promote comprehension while retaining communicative value (Cummins, 1984; Darian, 2001; Willis, 1996). As Tomlinson (2012) notes, learners benefit from frequent interactions with authentic tasks that prepare them for real-life communication by offering meaningful language exposure, affective involvement, and deeper processing.

To remain accessible, however, materials must align with learners' profiles, including prior educational experiences and language- and literacy-related skills as well as sociocultural contexts (Tomlinson, 2012; Trabelsi, 2010). Moreover, authenticity concerns not only what materials are used but how they are used: tasks should involve real communicative purposes and strategies to cope with partial comprehension (Widdowson, 1998). They can also stimulate affective engagement and deeper processing (Mishan, 2005). Authentic materials in adult education correlate with increased engagement in reading and writing practices beyond the classroom, thus fostering transfer to real-life literacy practices (Purcell-Gates et al., 2002). For LESLLA learners, meaningful and culturally grounded practices are essential for language and identity development, even if increased cognitive load must be addressed through pedagogical scaffolding such as enhanced input (Ellis, 1999; Tomlinson, 2012).

Methodology

The study adopts a participatory action research approach, emphasizing collaborative inquiry and practice-oriented development (Kemmis et al., 2013; Reason & Bradbury, 2001). This

approach was chosen to address the identified discrepancies between current SFI teaching practices and the everyday literacy needs of LESLLA learners. Over twelve months, the researcher and teachers acted as co-investigators in a joint exploration of literacy-oriented pedagogy in SFI, grounded in questions and challenges identified by the teachers themselves (Anderson et al., 2007). The process followed iterative cycles of planning, implementation, observation and reflection (Kemmis & McTaggart, 2005), through which teachers collaboratively planned and implemented changes involving authentic texts and related scaffolding strategies, observed students' engagement, and reflected on how teaching could become more relevant for students. Through these cycles, continuous adjustments were made, leading to a deeper understanding of how to create meaningful learning contexts by building on students' everyday literacy needs. Reflections were not only evaluative but generative, fostering new possibilities for action (Kemmis et al., 2013; Reason & Bradbury, 2001).

Data Collection

Empirical material was generated within the project *Literacy Development and Authenticity in Second Language Instruction in Swedish for Immigrants (2024–2025)*, conducted in collaboration between researchers and teachers to design contextually adapted practices using authentic materials. Data sources included:

- Field notes from five classroom observations of four teachers in study path 1 (with one or two observations per teacher)
- Four individual teacher interviews in the middle of iteration cycles
- Eight recorded and transcribed collegial reflections (evaluative and reflective) approximately every second month
- Nine completed questionnaires at the end of the project.

The action research cycles were initiated through collegial reflections, during which teachers and the researcher jointly identified focus areas, planned instructional changes, and followed up on their implementation in classroom practice. Data from collegial reflections and individual interviews were analyzed on an ongoing basis, with key insights summarized by the researcher to inform subsequent cycles. Field notes and teacher logs documented classroom practices and student responses, while questionnaires provided a summative perspective at the end of the project. Logs were not analyzed by the researcher, but they informed collegial reflections and, in some cases, individual interviews. Recorded collegial reflections captured teachers' shared learning over time, illustrating the dynamics of the action research process as participants identified benefits, challenges, and possible solutions. Individual interviews provided deeper insights into experiences with authentic texts, while end-of-project questionnaires offered a summative perspective. The project involved ten SFI teachers working across different courses and study paths, along with two language support staff, one special education teacher, and one program coordinator, all of whom participated in the questionnaires and collegial reflections. This article focuses on teachers working in study path 1, serving students with no prior formal schooling. These participants are presented in Table 1.

Table 1.*Teachers in focus in this study*

Teacher	Study path and course or other function	Class
Teacher 1	Alpha, 1A	Class 1
Teacher 2	1B	Class 2
Teacher 3	1C	Class 3
Teacher 4	1C	Class 4
LS1	Language support staff	Class 1-4
LS2	Language support staff	Class 1-4

Data from collegial reflections and questionnaires that include teachers from other study paths are also drawn on where relevant to the analysis.

Data Analysis

By combining these different data sources, methodological triangulation was achieved (Cohen et al., 2018), strengthening the credibility of the study and enabling a nuanced understanding of both the teaching practices and the teachers' reflections. The material was analyzed using reflexive thematic analysis, conducted inductively and iteratively, following Braun and Clarke's (2021) six phases: familiarization with the data, generating initial codes, constructing potential themes, reviewing and refining themes in relation to the dataset, defining and naming themes, and producing the report. Consistent with the participatory action research design, the analysis covered successive cycles of planning, implementation, observation, and reflection, allowing attention to both recurring patterns and shifts in teaching practices over time (Kemmis & McTaggart, 2005). Although developed inductively, the themes were continuously related to the research questions to ensure analytical rigor and coherence. The following five themes were constructed from collegial reflections, teacher interviews, questionnaires and field notes from classroom observations: 1) Authenticity as boundary-crossing practices, 2) Empowerment and situated learning, 3) Digital literacy as inclusion or exclusion, 4) Cognitive load and scaffolding strategies, and 5) Professional understanding and teacher development.

Ethical Considerations

The study followed Swedish ethical guidelines for educational research and the principles for research involving humans as outlined by the *Swedish Research Council* (2024). Participants were informed about the purpose of the project, the data use, and their right to withdraw. Written informed consent was obtained from all participants; responses were anonymous, and all data were de-identified and securely stored in compliance with the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). In line with the ethical foundations of participatory action research, the process emphasized democratic participation, transparency, and shared ownership of knowledge creation ensuring teachers actively shaped both the research focus and the interpretation of findings (Reason & Bradbury, 2001).

Findings

The findings are organized into the five analytically framed themes that emerged from thematic analysis and that capture recurring patterns as well as shifts in teachers' understanding and teaching practices over time. These themes address the research questions in complementary ways. *Authenticity as boundary-crossing practices* responds to the first research question concerning what characterizes the teaching practices involving authentic texts. *Empowerment and situated learning* and *Digital literacy as inclusion or exclusion* mainly respond to the second question regarding perceived benefits and challenges for learners in the use of authentic texts, while also addressing the third research question on how teachers perceive students' responses to working with authentic texts. The theme *Cognitive load and scaffolding strategies* likewise responds to the third research question. The theme *Professional understanding and teacher development* has a broader scope and highlights how iterative reflection within the action research process generated new insights and shaped teachers' professional understanding. Each theme is illustrated with key examples and interpreted in relation to the study's theoretical framework.

Authenticity as Boundary-Crossing Practice

This theme follows how teachers' initial concerns about the relevance of literacy teaching developed into practices that linked classroom work with students' everyday communicative needs. Early collegial reflections highlighted challenges such as interpreting official messages and supporting children's school communication, reinforced by students' frequent help requests with letters after class. By using authentic materials, such as SMS reminders, official notices, forms, and brochures as mediating tools, teaching brought the outside in (Baynham, 2006), connecting classroom activities with learners' everyday literacies and social participation.

- (1) We have encouraged the students to bring the SMS they have received with them – it gives so much to work with. (Teacher 2)
- (2) A student came with an email from the Swedish Public Employment Service. It turned out that a large part of the group had received the same "incomprehensible" email. We read it together and talked about difficult words. They were highly motivated to understand the email. (Teacher 3)

Across all five classroom observations, instruction was embedded in real social practices (Barton & Hamilton, 2000; Street, 1984). In Class 1 (Alpha/1A), a short, de-identified SMS from the *Public Dental Service* initiated whole-class work focused on identifying institutional roles and the action required by the message, using guiding questions (*Who is it from? Who is it for? What should you do?*), as demonstrated in Figures 1 and 2 below.

Figure 1.

A text message has arrived!

Figure 2.

Guiding questions (What is the message about? What will Sara have to do?)

With multimodal support, the teacher and language support staff facilitated joint meaning-making as students collaboratively identified key information, foregrounding functional reading strategies.

- (3) We focus on the most important things: who is it from, who is it for, what to do? (Teacher 1)

As the work progressed, the focus expanded beyond teacher-selected authentic texts to include learner-generated resources. This development was exemplified in the recycling theme, where teachers and language support staff first introduced photographs of household recycling spaces (see Figures 3 and 4), after which students contributed images and video recordings from their own neighborhoods.

Figure 3.*Teachers' recycling room*

By comparing signage, local routines and recycling practices, this sequencing anchored literacy work in lived experiences and enhanced its relevance through recognition, supporting meaning-making (Barton & Hamilton, 2000; Ivanič, 2009). Students' contributions, including photographs and video recordings of poorly maintained waste areas, were associated with increased engagement and strengthened social responsibility. Teachers' reflections underscore this point:

- (4) Today, a student [who came] had independently taken photos over the weekend. She also recorded footage showing areas where garbage was scattered everywhere outdoors. (Teacher 3)
- (5) I was so uplifted by what we did with the recycling – they were so interested when they had taken photos of the same things at home [and compared them]. It's a way of working that can be copied again. (Teacher 1)

These practices fostered curiosity and meaningful language use that students could apply beyond the classroom, drawing on their knowledge of the surrounding environment. The teachers'

responsive use of students' contributions reflects pedagogical contingency (Baynham, 2006), as instructional trajectories shifted in response to learner-initiated resources and questions. In Class 3, student photos functioned as mediating resources for discussions on transport disruptions and local history, where images such as a railway notice board led to vocabulary development, pragmatic interpretation, and community knowledge sharing, while a photo of a local church ruin inspired talk about historical architecture, drawing parallels to leisure activities in students' home countries.

- (6) I can see [now] that the passive knowledge that the students have gained through social information when they came to Sweden comes to life.
(Teacher 2)

Work with authentic texts was sometimes complemented by scaffolding activities such as role-plays, used to rehearse everyday interactions like buying medicine or rescheduling appointments. These activities supported the transfer of classroom learning to everyday contexts (*bringing the inside out* [Baynham, 2006]), and identity negotiation as language users. In Class 2, dental service texts were sequenced to gradually increase cognitive demand, moving from short SMS ("book", "cancel", "rebook") to longer formal summons with complex institutional vocabulary (e.g. "summons", "routine examination", "cancellation fee"). This progression, supported by scaffolding, aligns with principles of enhanced input (Ellis, 1999) and cognitive load management (Tomlinson, 2012). Integrating authentic texts with structured support enabled learners to decode institutional language while reinforcing relevance. Authentic texts also functioned as *boundary objects* (Akkerman & Bakker, 2011), linking classroom practices to social life and *bringing the outside in* (Baynham, 2006).

This shows that authenticity is a process of meaning-making rather than mere material selection. Teachers scaffolded meaning-making by addressing texts' purpose and function rather than formal structures, consistent with principles of meaningful learning (Ausubel, 1968) and fostering strategic competences, such as recognizing sender-recipient relations, identifying different types of numbers (e.g. phone numbers, dates), and determining required actions. Across groups, as observed in classroom interaction and discussed in teacher reflections during the process, tasks increasingly focused on real communicative purposes rather than decontextualized form practice (Gilmore, 2007; Michan, 2005; Widdowson, 1978). This reflects a gradual shift from working with authentic texts toward student-initiated meaning-making.

Empowerment and Situated Learning

This theme illustrates how shifts in literacy practices were reflected in increased student empowerment, as learners assumed greater responsibility for meaning-making and action beyond the classroom. Classroom work fostered agency and autonomy among LESLLA students, who often lack established strategies for text processing (Kurvers et al., 2015). Teachers reported heightened engagement and initiative when students contributed with their own materials (e.g. photos, SMS, letters), experiences, and questions, and transferred classroom strategies to everyday life, reflecting a movement toward *bringing the inside out* or *the outside in* (Baynham, 2006). Such practices align with situated learning (Lave & Wenger, 1991) and critical pedagogy and empowerment (Freire, 1970/1993) as they create dialogic spaces for negotiation of meaning. Teachers observed that authentic texts prompted discussions extending beyond decoding to include

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strategies for managing digital information and broader social issues such as justice, gender, equality and interactions with public authorities. As one teacher noted:

- (7) Learning to read important messages is also about taking control of your situation in the family – not having to hand everything over to the children. (Teacher 4)

Another reflected:

- (8) The students get more space to be active in the lessons without "ready-made" answers. I feel that the students are engaged. After the [...] work [in this project] with text messages/letters in the theme of health, a student has told us that they have started to read letters they have received. In the past, they left the letters to relatives without even opening them. (Teacher 1)

Such episodes illustrate how literacy learning may reshape roles and responsibilities, as in the case where:

- (9) A mother was able to explain HPV vaccination to her daughter thanks to the lesson – it changes the whole division of roles at home. (collegial reflections)

These practices enabled forms of empowerment, allowing some students to take responsibility for everyday communicative practices and negotiate meaning across contexts (Freire, 1970/1993; Lave & Wenger, 1991). By creating space for student initiative, instruction becomes more dialogical and socially transformative, consistent with theories of situated learning, critical pedagogy and student agency. This theme shows how everyday literacy bridges school-related literacy (Ivanič, 2009) and, through motivation and perceived usefulness linked to authenticity (Gilmore, 2007; Renders & Benson, 2017), supports a shift toward greater responsibility, initiative, and agency in everyday communicative practices.

Digital Literacy as Inclusion or Exclusion

This theme illustrates how digital literacy gradually developed, as teaching shifted from identifying barriers to mediating access and participation. Digital literacy emerged as both a key competence for societal participation and a persistent instructional challenge, as limited access (e.g. lack of phone subscriptions) and varying digital skills constrained participation. Teachers responded with targeted support, including loaned tablets, to mitigate these disparities. Classroom tasks incorporated authentic digital gateways, such as logging into the municipal library website, using local transport apps to plan journeys, rescheduling trips, interpreting delays, scanning QR codes, following links, and reading web pages connected to SMS. By engaging with codes, links, and online platforms, learners navigated boundary-crossing between offline and online practices. These activities positioned teachers and language support staff as mediators across this divide (Akkerman & Bakker, 2011). Over time, this mediating role became more systematic, as teachers refined their scaffolding in response to observed digital challenges among learners.

- (10) We went into Xstad's library and logged in. The password is the last four digits of the social security number. Then we could renew the book. (collegial reflections)

- (11) I've talked about X-traffic's app [public transportation] – how to see when the train is leaving and how to plan the journey. (collegial reflections)

Work with authentic digital texts thus served as an entry point to digital literacy while also revealing risks of exclusion linked to digital divides. The teachers' mediating role was central and involved concrete scaffolding practices such as jointly interpreting digital messages and providing step-by-step support in basic digital navigation.

Cognitive Load and Scaffolding Strategies

This theme captures how teachers' understanding of cognitive load and text complexity developed over time, shaping more leveled-adapted scaffolding strategies. Institutional texts were found to challenge LESLLA students' independent comprehension, due to lexical, syntactic and layout-related demands, prompting teachers to adopt flexible, differentiated support such as task breaking down, visual aids, and pace adjustment. One teacher noted:

- (12) Line breaks in text messages make students unable to understand dates.
(questionnaire)

Such observations underscore that difficulties extend beyond word meaning to text structure and multimodal interpretation (Altherr Flores, 2019). In collegial reflections, teachers increasingly drew attention to semantic complexity and cultural conventions embedded in institutional language:

- (13) There are so many layers in these texts – a word like 'folktandvården' [the Public Dental Service] can become 'Folkets park' [Peoples Park] in the students' interpretation. (collegial reflections)

In response, teachers began to experiment with pedagogical strategies aimed at managing cognitive load. Institutional texts were found to involve complex vocabulary and culturally embedded conventions, such as “rescheduling” and “mandatory registration”, which increased processing demands for LESLLA students (Tomlinson, 2012). These challenges are partly linked to limited phonological processing ability (Ardila et al., 2010; Huettig, 2015) but are also shaped by difficulties in integrating textual, visual, and contextual cues in multimodal institutional texts (Altherr Flores, 2019), highlighting the need for adapted tasks rather than simplified texts (Willis, 1996). Teachers therefore proposed strategies such as joint interpretation of SMS messages, role-play, and listening exercises, to leverage auditory strengths and scaffold written production. This process of teachers' iterative refinement of practice underscored the importance of multimodal support and explicit attention to cultural conventions with careful sequencing and scaffolding, to transform cognitive demands into meaningful learning opportunities (Tomlinson, 2012; Willis, 1996).

Professional Understanding and Teacher Development

This theme illustrates how teachers' professional understanding developed throughout the action research process, as recurring classroom challenges prompted reconsideration of instructional priorities and assumptions about student participation. Teachers noted persistent difficulties with institutional language across course levels, indicating a need for sustained

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pedagogical support regardless of progression. Over time, they also gained deeper insight into the cultural and social dimensions of students' everyday lives, including issues related to privacy, parental roles, and gender equality, recognizing how language mediated power relations within families and shaped learners' opportunities for participation.

- (14) I have discovered what is difficult to understand even though we have practiced it many times, an example is dates and times. Even though I started lessons every day by talking about dates, writing dates on the board in different ways, talking about times, etc., I discovered that the students had a very hard time with it. (Teacher 2)

Such observations illustrate how teachers' understanding of students' literacy challenges became more fine-grained, shifting attention from surface comprehension to underlying structural, semantic, and cultural complexity. Reflections highlighted the importance of collegial collaboration between teachers and language support staff as a key prerequisite for successful implementation, consistent with participatory principles of action research, which stress shared responsibility for change (Reason & Bradbury, 2001). Through iterative cycles of planning, implementing, observing, and reflecting (Kemmis & McTaggart, 2005; Kemmis et al., 2013), teachers co-constructed instructional strategies such as role-plays, photo assignments, and digital training, strengthening the research-informed basis of teaching and enhancing professional agency (Cochran-Smith & Lytle, 1999). These processes also contributed to a shift in teachers' expectations regarding student capacity and participation, even at early levels of literacy development. Teachers reported a shift in perspective on student activity:

- (15) Even at beginner levels, students can contribute substantially to lesson content. [The project] has made me more aware of the importance of student activity and their contribution to all aspects of teaching. [...] I now consider during the planning stage how students can be active and contribute with their knowledge and experiences. Previously, I probably did not think this was possible given their language level but as time goes on, it is increasingly feasible. (Questionnaire)

Taken together, the findings show how sustained engagement with classroom challenges supported professional learning through dialogic examination of practice, enabling teachers to adjust instruction in response to empirical observation rather than fixed assumptions and positioning them as reflexive practitioners (Cochran-Smith & Lytle, 1999).

Discussion

This study investigated how authentic texts were used in SFI instruction for LESLLA learners and how teachers perceived their impact on engagement, learning, and teaching practice. Teaching practices involving authentic texts were characterized by a practice-oriented, functional and multimodal approach, based on students' communicative needs, in which authentic texts drawn from learners' everyday lives such as institutional messages or letters from the *Public Dental Service*, were used for joint meaning-making. Instruction initially focused on text purpose and communicative roles, and gradually shifted toward more student-initiated resources, supported

by pedagogical mediation such as role-plays related to rescheduling appointments. Through iterative experimentation with texts, activities and student contributions, teachers shaped instruction in practice (Anderson et al., 2007; Perry et al., 2018), creating meaningful and socially situated learning opportunities consistent with literacy as social practice (Barton & Hamilton, 2000; Street, 1984). In this process, authentic texts functioned as boundary objects (Akkerman & Bakker, 2011), linking classroom activities with learners' everyday lives and enabling communicative participation beyond the classroom (Purcell-Gates et al., 2002).

Benefits and challenges identified by teachers for learners included perceived relevance, increased engagement, motivation, and opportunities for learner agency. Engagement was evident both in the classroom participation and in learners' growing willingness to read, interpret and act on institutional texts independently beyond school. Teachers described instances where students began to handle letters concerning vaccination or other types of institutional texts on their own, reducing reliance on children as informal interpreters and reasserting parental responsibility in family-related communication. For LESLLA learners with predominantly oral and practical literacy backgrounds, such examples illustrate how contextualized instruction can support sustained engagement and participation (Bigelow & Vinogradov, 2011; Condelli et al., 2008). At the same time, the findings confirm persistent challenges related to authentic institutional texts, including cognitive loads, culturally embedded conventions (Altherr Flores, 2019; Tomlinson, 2012) and digital barriers. These challenges highlight the need for carefully sequenced tasks and adapted scaffolding rather than text simplification (Willis, 1996).

Overall, the findings illustrate how teachers perceived students' responses to working with authentic texts as supporting participation in meaningful social practices, including the use of learner-generated texts and experiences. These responses were understood as contributing to incremental development of empowerment and autonomy, enabling learners to negotiate meaning and act more independently in everyday communicative contexts within both family life and society, consistent with situated learning perspectives (Lave & Wenger, 1991) and extending earlier research on empowerment, authenticity and learner autonomy (Freire, 1970/1993; Gilmore, 2007; Reinders & Benson, 2017).

Conclusions and Implications

This study shows how working with authentic texts in LESLLA instruction can support both language development and social inclusion by enabling learners to participate more actively in everyday communicative practices. Through collegial reflection and shared inquiry, teachers were able to examine and gradually refine existing instructional practices in response to recurring classroom challenges. Rather than indicating a fundamental pedagogical shift, the findings point to increased precision and responsiveness in teachers' understanding of learners' needs and of institutional literacy demands. The participatory action research framework provided structured opportunities for systematic reflection on practice, supporting instructional adjustments over time. The study thus offers empirically grounded insights into collaborative professional learning in adult second language and literacy education, with implications for teacher education and for the development of pedagogical approaches that are responsive to the realities of LESLLA instruction (Cochran-Smith & Lytle, 1999; Piccinin & Dal Maso, 2021)

References

- Altherr Flores, J. A. (2019). Messages and meaning in perceived and lived spaces: Semiosis, institutions and landscapes. *European Journal of Applied Linguistics and TEFL*, 8(1), 175-202.
- Anderson, G. L., Herr, K., & Nihlen, A. S. (2007). *Studying your own school: An educator's guide to practitioner action research* (2nd ed.). Corwin Press.
- Barton, D. (2007). *Literacy. An Introduction to the Ecology of Written Language*. Blackwell.
- Ardila, A., Bertolucci, P. H., Braga, L. W., Castro-Caldas, A., Judd, T., Kosmidis, M. H., & Rosselli, M. (2010). Illiteracy: The neuropsychology of cognition without reading. *Archives of Clinical Neuropsychology*, 25(8), 689–712. <https://doi.org/10.1093/arclin/acq079>
- Ausubel, D. P. (1968). *Educational psychology: A cognitive view*. Holt, Rinehart and Winston Inc.
- Barton, D., & Hamilton, M. E. (2000). *Local literacies: Reading and writing in one community*. Routledge.
- Baynham, M. (2006). Agency and contingency in the language learning of refugees and asylum seekers. *Linguistics and Education*, 17(1), 24–39. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.linged.2006.08.008>
- Berardo, S. A., (2006). The use of authentic materials in the teaching of reading. *The Reading Matrix*, 6(2), 60–69.
- Bigelow, M., & Vinogradov, P. (2011). Teaching adult second language learners who are emergent readers. *Annual Review of Applied Linguistics*, 31, 120-136. <https://doi.org/10.1017/s0267190511000109>
- Bigelow, M., & Tarone, E. (2004). The role of literacy level in second language acquisition: Doesn't who we study determine what we know? *TESOL Quarterly*, 38(4), 689–700. <https://doi.org/10.2307/3588285>
- Bigelow, M., & Schwarz, R. L. (2010). *Adult English language learners with limited literacy*. National Institute for Literacy.
- Bigelow, M., & Watson, J. (2013). The role of educational level, literacy, and orality in L2 learning. *The Routledge handbook of second language acquisition*, 461-475.
- Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2021). *Thematic analysis: A practical guide*. SAGE Publications Ltd.
- Breen, M. (1985). Authenticity in the language classroom. *Applied Linguistics*, 6(1), 60–70.
- Buendgens-Kosten, J. (2014). Authenticity. *ELT journal*, 68(4), 457-459. <https://doi.org/10.1093/elt/ccu034>
- Cochran-Smith, M., & Lytle, S. L. (1999). The teacher research movement: A decade later. *Educational Researcher*, 28(7), 15–25. <https://doi.org/10.3102/0013189X028007015>
- Cohen, L., Manion, L., & Morrison, K. (2018). *Research methods in education* (8th ed.). Routledge.
- Colliander, H., Ahn, S. E., & Andersson, P. (2018). Actions and conceptions: Exploring initial literacy teaching practice for adults. *Journal of Language, Identity & Education*, 17(5), 306–319. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15348458.2018.1465344>
- Condelli, L., Wrigley, H. S., & Yoon, K. S. (2008). “What works” for adult literacy students of English as a second language. In S. M. Reder & J. Bynner (Eds.), *Tracking adult literacy and numeracy skills: Findings from longitudinal research* (pp. 132–159). Routledge.

- Cummins, J. (1984). Bilingualism and cognitive functioning. In S. Shapson & V. D'Oyley (Eds.), *Bilingual and Multicultural Education: Canadian Perspectives* (pp. 55–70). Multilingual Matters.
- Darian, S. (2001). Adapting authentic materials for language teaching. *English Teaching Forum*, 39(2), 27–40.
- Da Silva, C., Faísca, L., Ingvar, M., Petersson, K. M., & Reis, A. (2012). Literacy: Exploring working memory systems. *Journal of Clinical and Experimental Neuropsychology*, 34(4), 369–377. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13803395.2011.645017>
- Engeström, Y., Engeström, R., & Kärkkäinen, M. (1995). Polycontextuality and boundary crossing in expert cognition: Learning and problem solving in complex work activities. *Learning and Instruction*, 5(4), 319–336. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0959-4752\(95\)00021-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/0959-4752(95)00021-6)
- Ellis, R. (1999). Input-based approaches to teaching grammar: A review of classroom-oriented research. *Annual Review of Applied Linguistics*, 19, 64–80. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0267190599190044>
- Franker, Q. (2011). *Litteracitet och visuella texter: Studier om lärare och kortutbildade deltagare i sfi* [Literacies and Visual Texts. Studies on Teachers and Low Educated Learners in the Basic Swedish Language Programme for Adult Immigrants]. Doctoral dissertation: Department of Language Education, Stockholms universitet.
- Freire, P. (1970/1993). *Pedagogy of the oppressed* (30th anniversary ed.). Continuum.
- Gilmore, A. (2007). Authentic materials and authenticity in foreign language learning. *Language teaching*, 40(2), 97–118.
- Huettig, F. (2015). Literacy influences cognitive abilities far beyond the mastery of written language. *LESLLA Symposium Proceedings*, 10(1), 115–127. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.802439>
- Hyltenstam, K. & Milani, T. (2012). Flerspråkighetens sociopolitiska och sociokulturella ramar [Socio-political and socio-cultural framework of multilingualism]. In M. Axelsson, K. Hyltenstam, & I. Lindberg (Eds.), *Flerspråkighet: en forskningsöversikt* [Multilingualism: A research review] (pp. 17–133). Vetenskapsrådet [Swedish research Council]. <https://www.vr.se/analys/rapporter/vara-rapporter/2012-06-01-flersprakighet---en-forskningsoversikt.html>
- Ivanič, R. (2009). Bringing literacy studies into research on learning across the curriculum. In M. Baynham & M. Prinsloo (Eds.), *The future of literacy studies* (pp. 100–122). Palgrave Macmillan. https://doi.org/10.1057/9780230245693_6
- Jehoul, A., Van Nuffel, H., & Schiepers, M. (2025). Blend up: Empowering LESLLA learners through blended learning. *ReCALL*, 37(2), 157–173. <https://doi.org/10.1017/s0958344024000363>
- Kemmis, S. (2005). Participatory Action Research: Communicative action and the public sphere. In N. K. Denzin & Y. S. Lincoln (Eds.), *The Sage handbook of qualitative research* (3rd ed., pp. 559–603). Sage Publications.
- Kemmis, S., McTaggart, R., & Nixon, R. (2013). *The action research planner: Doing critical participatory action research*. Springer Science & Business Media.
- Klein, W., & Perdue, C. (1992). *Utterance structure: Developing grammars again*. John Benjamins.
- Kurvers, J., & van de Craats, I. (2007). Memory, second language reading, and lexicon: A comparison between successful and less successful adults and children. *LESLLA Symposium Proceedings*, 2(1), 65–80. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7992924>

- Kurvers, J., van de Craats, I., & van Hout, R. (2015). Footprints for the future: Cognition, literacy and Second Language learning by adults. *LESLLA Symposium Proceedings*, 10(1), 7–32. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8024359>
- Lave, J., & Wenger, E. (1991). *Situated learning: Legitimate peripheral participation*. Cambridge University Press.
- Lindberg, I., & Sandwall, K. (2007). Nobody’s darling? Swedish for adult immigrants: A critical perspective. *Prospect: An Australian Journal of TESOL*, 22(3), 79–95.
- Mishan, F. (2005). *Designing authenticity into language learning materials*. Intellect.
- Minuz, F., Kurvers, J., Schramm, K., Rocca, L., & Naeb, R. (2022). *Literacy and second language learning for the linguistic integration of adult migrants: Reference guide*. Council of Europe.
- Perry, K. H., Shaw, D. M., Ivanyuk, L., & Tham, Y. S. S. (2018). The “of courseness” of functional literacy: Ideologies in adult literacy. *Journal of Literacy Research*, 50(1), 74–96. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1086296x17753262>
- Piccinin, S., & Dal Maso, S. (2021). Promoting literacy in adult second language learners: A systematic review of effective practices. *Languages*, 6(3), 127. <https://doi.org/10.3390/languages6030127>
- Purcell-Gates, V., Degener, S. C., Jacobson, E., & Soler, M. (2002). Impact of authentic adult literacy instruction on adult literacy practices. *Reading Research Quarterly*, 37(1), 70–92. <https://doi.org/10.1598/rrq.37.1.3>
- Reason, P., & Bradbury, H. (Eds.). (2001). *Handbook of action research: Participative inquiry and practice*. SAGE.
- Reinders, H., & Benson, P. (2017). Research agenda: Language learning beyond the classroom. *Language Teaching*, 50(4), 561–578 <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0261444817000192>
- Sandwall, K. (2013). *Att Hantera Praktiken — Om Sfi -Studeraendes Möjligheter till Interaktion och Lärande på Praktikplatser*. [Managing the internship: On the opportunities for SFI students' interaction and learning in internship settings]. Doctoral Dissertation: Gothenburg Studies in Nordic Linguistics 20: Gothenburg: University of Gothenburg.
- Sexton, S. S. (2025). Meaningful learning—David P. Ausubel. In B. Akpan & T.J. Kennedy (Eds.) *Science education in theory and practice: An introductory guide to learning theory* (pp. 157–171). Springer Nature Switzerland.
- Skiada, M., (2021). The implementation of authentic language input in second language (L2) teaching: Pedagogical arguments. *Training, Language and Culture*, 5(1), 86–96. <https://doi.org/10.22363/2521-442x-2021-5-1-86-96>
- SOU 2020:66. (2020). *Samverkande krafter – för stärkt kvalitet och likvärdighet inom komvux för elever med svenska som andraspråk: Betänkande av KLIVA-utredningen* [Coordinated efforts – strengthening quality and equity in municipal adult education for learners of Swedish as a second language]. Stockholm: Swedish Government Official Reports, Ministry of Education.
- Statistics Sweden. (2024). *PIAAC: Den internationella undersökningen av vuxnas färdigheter. Temarapport 2024:4* [PIAAC: The international survey of adult skills. Thematic report 2024:4]. https://www.scb.se/contentassets/43fec92b83c24a60aebb22150d6d59fa/uf0546_2022a01_br_a40br2404.pdf
- Street, B. (1984). *Literacy in theory and practice*. Cambridge University Press.

- Swedish National Agency for Education [Skolverket]. (2024). *Syllabus for municipal adult education in Swedish tuition for immigrants (SFI)*. Skolverket. https://www.skolverket.se/download/18.4fc05a3f164131a7418ce9/1535097772538/Kursplan_sfi_engelska.pdf
- Swedish Research Council [Vetenskapsrådet]. (2024). *Good research practice*. Vetenskapsrådet. <https://www.vr.se/english/analysis/reports/our-reports/2025-07-03-good-research-practice-2024.html>
- Swedish Schools Inspectorate. (2018) *Undervisning i Svenska för Invandrare: Kvalitetsgranskning [Teaching Swedish for immigrants: Quality review]*; Swedish Schools Inspectorate: Stockholm, Sweden, 2018. <https://www.skolinspektionen.se/globalassets/02-beslut-rapporter-stat/granskningsrapporter/tkg/2018/sfi/svenska-for-invandrare---kvalitetsgranskning-2018.pdf.pdf>
- Swedish Schools Inspectorate. (2024) *En granskning av kommunal vuxenutbildning i svenska för invandrare (SFI). Redovisning av regeringsuppdrag, U2021/04942. Rapport 2024:1** [A review of municipal adult education in Swedish for immigrants (SFI). Report on a government assignment, U2021/04942. Report 2024:1] Swedish Schools Inspectorate: Stockholm, Sweden, 2024. <https://www.skolinspektionen.se/globalassets/02-beslut-rapporter-stat/granskningsrapporter/tkg/2018/sfi/svenska-for-invandrare---kvalitetsgranskning-2018.pdf>
- Tomlinson, B. (2012). Materials development for language learning and teaching. *Language Teaching*, 45(2), 143–179. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003106609-11>
- Trabelsi, S. (2010). Developing and trialing authentic materials for business English students at a Tunisian university. In B. Tomlinson & H. Masuhara (Eds.), *Research for materials development in language learning: Evidence for best practice* (pp. 103–120). <https://doi.org/10.5040/9781474211949.ch-007>
- Wedin, Å. & Norlund Shaswar, A. N. (2019). Interaction in the adult L2-classroom: The case of Swedish for Immigrants in Sweden. *APPLES – Journal of Applied Language Studies*, 13(2), 45–64. <https://doi.org/10.17011/apples/urn.201903251959>
- Wedin, Å., & Shaswar, A. N. (2023). Teachers’ perceptions of letter learning among adults: The case of basic literacy education in Swedish for immigrants. *Nordic Journal of Literacy Research*, 9(1), 39–58. <https://doi.org/10.23865/njlr.v9.3843>
- Wedin, Å., & Berg, L. (2024). Multiliteracies and translanguaging pedagogy in the adult L2-classroom: The case of basic literacy education in Swedish for Immigrants. *Apples-Journal of Applied Language Studies*, 18(2), 76–92. <https://doi.org/10.47862/apples.110859>
- Wedin, Å. (2024a) Becoming an independent Swedish citizen: Critical literacy as a tool for multilingual literacies in Swedish for Immigrants. *Studies in the Education of Adults*, 56(1), 26-42, <https://doi.org/10.1080/02660830.2023.2171097>
- Wedin, Å. (2024b). Teachers’ perceptions of basic literacy teaching: The case of basic literacy in education for adult L2 learners in Sweden. *Nordic Journal of Literacy Research*, 10(3). <https://doi.org/10.23865/njlr.v10.6045>
- Widdowson, H. G. (1978). *Teaching language as communication*. Oxford University Press.
- Widdowson, H. G. (1998). Context, community, and authentic language. *TESOL Quarterly*, 32(4), 705–716. <https://doi.org/10.2307/3588001>
- Willis, J. (1996). *A framework for task-based learning*. Longman Pearson.